

Family Fragmentation in The Vultures by Vijay Tendulkar

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Abstract:

The Vultures is considered one of Vijay Tendulkar's best plays. The play possesses various themes. However, family fragmentation is one of the dominant themes Vijay Tendulkar employs to explore the true nature of human beings in the context of the traditional culture of typical Indian families, which are strict, rigid, and orthodox about their beliefs, ritual practices, and way of life. Vijay Tendulkar was a renowned playwright, a prominent journalist, and an esteemed film writer. He is known for his rebellious comments and criticisms on the age-old thoughts of Indians regarding women, castes, and religions. The present paper is dealt with in light of the fragmentation of the Pitale family. The family is notorious for their greed, unlimited hunger, illicit relationships, disrespect, dishonesty, unfaithfulness, and lack of love.

Keywords: The Vultures, Vijay Tendulkar, Family and Fragmentation

Introduction:

The present paper proposes to describe an issue of family fragmentation in Vijay Tendulkar's play *The Vultures*. It is a remarkable play by Vijay Tendulkar. First, it was written in the Marathi language as a "Gidhade" for the Marathi theatre. Later, it was translated into English by Priya Adarkar. Extreme greed, hunger for money and property, and the deep-rooted vices of human beings are the major themes predominantly found in *The Vultures*. Due to greed and hunger, each character attempts to control the other's life, and neither allows the other to share the father's property. Vijay Tendulkar is known as a modern playwright of Indian Theatre. His literary works make a revolt against the orthodox, feudal and patriarchal tendency by which society is controlled, women are denied liberty, and politicians produce religious and social groups.

Vijay Tendulkar was born in a Brahmin family on 06th January 1928. His father was a publisher, writer and theatre artist. The liberal culture of the family made Vijay Tendulkar more open-minded, democratic, and modern. As his mother would often tell him stories about the independence movement, Lokmanya Tilak and Mahatma Gandhi, on the other hand, he read many books of English literature and watched many Hollywood movies. This helped him to think broadly, be liberal with all, and welcome new approaches openly. He openly addressed neglected issues in his plays, short stories, and articles. Exploitation of women, orphans, and lower caste people, poverty, lust, and injustice with the ordinary masses, hypocrisy, jealousy, immorality and domestic violence are the themes that have occupied the major space in his work of art. He was considered a pioneer of modern Marathi theatre and literature. The lust, hunger and violence in the family lead to fragmentation

of the family. As a social commentator, he projects the harsh and hard realities of Indian society. His great contribution to Indian literature has been recognized with various esteemed and prestigious awards conferred on him by government agencies, including the Sahitya Akademi Award, the Sangeet Natak Akademi Award, the Maharashtra Gaurav Puraskar 1990, and the Government of India's prestigious Padma Bhushan award.

The Vultures, a play by Vijay Tendulkar, is full of greed, selfishness, betrayal, loveless family life and domestic violence. In 1961, it was written in Marathi in two acts about the Pitale family. The play created controversy in Marathi literature and the contemporary society of Maharashtra when it was published in 1971. As the play enlarges, the deep-rooted evils of conservative Marathi society. While talking about Pappa's family, Vijay Tendulkar says, this house was a hole in a tree where Vultures used to live in the shape of human beings. Pappa Pitale is the head of a family; he has three sons, like Ramakant, Umakant, and Rajnikant, and one illegitimate son, one daughter, Manik and one daughter-in-law, Rama. Except Rajnikant and daughter-in-law Rama, other members of the Pitale family bear all the qualities of Vultures. They are extremely greedy, voracious, and insatiable about wealth and property. These vulture qualities do not allow them to respect and love each other. Using the grey colour for the drawing room and bedroom, the playwright shows that no one is happy in the house. On the contrary, the green colour of the garage and Tulsi Vrindavan, where Rajnikant would stay alone, indicates that positive waves prevail there. They are fragmented into family members. Generally, it is universal that a father wants growth, prosperity, and development and peace for his children, but in the play, Pappa curses his children and says, *"If I die, it'll be a release! They're all waiting for*

it. But I'm your own father. After all! If I die, I'll become a ghost. I'll sit on your chest! I won't let you enjoy a rupee of it. I earned it all. Now, these wolves, these bullies!." [209] He calls his children bastards and scoundrels. He blames his wife for her death and claims that she has left all these bastards with him. He also confesses it was his big mistake to produce them. On the other hand, elder son Ramakant also disrespects his father, *"'A bloody burden on the earth' and ironically replied that as the seed, so the tree"*. All these characters are very materialistic and practical; they do not hesitate to betray their closest ones. Head of the family, Pappa Pitale, was the first to betray his brother Sakharam in their business. Pappa Pitale and Sakharam Pitale built a construction firm, "The Hari Sakharam Company", and they took a lot of effort to run this company successfully. As time goes on, Pappa Pitale takes this company from his brother Sakharam by means of cheating and treachery. It results in Sakharam Pitale finding himself on the street. Here, the father is the first member of the Pitale family who cheats his blood relatives and does not feel any shame for his devilish acts. Hence, Pappa Pitale's children follow the footprints left behind by their father. As the saying as "you sow, so you reap" Pappa's sons and a daughter plot against their father, and they are waiting to drive him out one day. These children come to know that their father has some hidden money. To get this, Ramakant and Umakant forcibly put their father between them; their father is so afraid that he wants to call the police, but the phone was kept far away from his vicinity. Pappa is sure that his daughter is also involved in this plan, so he calls her "whore."

The two sons of Pappa are very cruel and cold-blooded; they dislike their sister Manik as a partner of the property. Manik does not possess the innate qualities of a woman, as mercy, love, sympathy and forgiveness, which enhance the

beauty of a woman. Instead, she likes to smoke cigarettes and consume wine when she feels alone and insecure in her own home. She closes all the doors of her room at night as she does not believe in her brothers; she always thinks that she will be killed. Violence and selfishness are deeply rooted in the play, and that disgraces their relations ruthlessly. When Ramakant and Umakant came to know that their sister was having a love affair with Raja Hondur, they decided to get rupees 25000 from him. They tortured Manik by fracturing her leg and also kicked Manik's belly to abort the baby. She became helpless with a broken leg and a white saree with blood.

Ramakant does not have faith in himself; he doubts the fertility of his wife Rama, although she is very confident that her womb is healthy and sound, and she is born to become a mother, but if the seed is soaked in poison i.e. liquor, if it is feeble, lifeless, devoid of virtue—then it is useless to blame fertile soil. Because of Ramakant's regular drink, Rama has tired and says, "Those women long ago who used to commit sati, we're all praise for them. They used to burn themselves alive—in loyalty to their dead husbands. But only once. Once they were burnt, they escaped. But...I commit sati every moment! I burn! I am consumed!" (242) Eventually, Ramakant curses his wife for having his step-brother's baby in her womb.

Conclusion:

Having too much interest in materialistic life, particularly a share in property and wealth, which each character expects from others. Their hunger and greed for money led to disrupting the peaceful life, the healthy nature of every member, and the unity of the family. For the money, each member, except Rajnikant and Rama, is ready to kill the others. Evil, greed and violence prevailed deeply in the mind of every character of the play. Hence, the family members are emotionally detached, have lost empathy, and care that they have to show for each other. This ultimately leads to fragmenting their relationship with one another as a family member of the Pitale family.

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